

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

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Smith and Doran examine the integration of smart energy management systems in agricultural operations, emphasizing the role of real-time monitoring and automated controls in optimizing energy consumption. Their research shows that intelligent systems can reduce energy waste by up to 25% while enhancing operational efficiency.

Overall, the literature demonstrates that efficient energy resource management and electrification in agriculture are key factors for sustainable development. The integration of renewable energy technologies, smart systems, and energy-efficient machinery plays a crucial role in improving productivity and reducing environmental impacts.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research utilized data from scientific articles, international reports on energy efficiency, and case studies on agricultural electrification. Primary data was gathered from renewable energy projects, while secondary data included official statistics and technological reviews. The collected data were analyzed using comparative analysis, energy efficiency assessments, and content analysis to evaluate the impact of energy resource optimization and electrification on agricultural productivity and sustainability.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

As in all sectors of the national economy, the supply and use of electricity is of great importance in agriculture. In agriculture, electricity is mainly used for lighting, heating, that is, electrification of greenhouses, pumping stations, electrification of stationary and mobile irrigation units, creation of a microclimate in hatcheries and livestock farms, etc. The problems of the quality of initial indicators used to determine the effectiveness of electrification of agricultural sectors are currently relevant. Importance of this topic:

- Electrification is an important factor of technical progress.
- Electrification of production process in agriculture.
- Problems of efficient use of electricity.

The energy system of Uzbekistan now fully meets the electricity needs of the republic's economy and population, and partially exports electricity to neighboring countries. At the same time, efforts are being made to use alternative sources of energy (solar, wind energy, etc.) in the energy system of Uzbekistan [4]. A number of large sectors of production infrastructure serving agriculture remain state-owned, including power transmission, roads, basic transport and other similar sectors. These industries have been and should remain state-owned, as in developed countries. Because in the conditions of market relations, since there are only a few such large industries, if they are privatized, it is possible that large monopolists will appear. As in all sectors of the national economy, the supply and use of electricity is of great importance in agriculture [5] (picture 2).

Picture 2. Solar panels.

The following are the primary indicators for determining the effectiveness of electrification of agriculture: cultivation of agricultural products on the land area and plowed land in kind and in cash; production of livestock products in terms of their number according to the type of animals and in terms of money; the number and power of electric motors, electrical apparatus, devices by sectors and processes, the value of electrification means (substations, power transmission networks, mechanisms), annual energy consumption by all economic sectors, the value of 39 kW power, the number of service personnel, labor costs for the production of agricultural products before and after electrification, the availability of electricity to farms, all these are factors of production

processes. characterizes the possibilities of electrification [6]. The more solid and reliable the construction of electricity transmission networks and distribution and production facilities is, the more effective functioning of not only agriculture, but also all sectors of the national economy will be ensured. The role of this network in agriculture is very important because, firstly, it ensures the continuous operation of water lifting devices in the processes related to crop irrigation, and secondly, the preservation of certain types of cultivated products in warehouses and refrigerators without damage. In addition, the power transmission network has an effect on increasing the quality and quantity of the products produced in the livestock industry or in the poultry industry during the use of electricity. Full electrification of agricultural production increases labor productivity and reduces production costs. The main areas of electrification in agriculture include:

Automation of irrigation systems. The use of electricity allows efficient use of water pumps and control systems. This process serves to save water resources and optimal growth of crops.

Livestock electrification. With the help of electrified systems, the processes of animal husbandry, feed distribution, heating and ventilation of farms are automated. This not only increases efficiency, but also ensures the health and productivity of animals.

Processing and storage of products. Electricity is needed to dry fruits, operate refrigeration systems for storage rooms, and automate food processing processes [7].

The construction of electric power stations shortens the period of reimbursement of electricity supply costs and improves the living conditions of rural residents. Fully supplying agriculture with electricity improves the quality of the products grown and reduces the demand for labor. The use of electric energy in agriculture creates the possibility of mechanization of crop irrigation, reduces labor costs by 10-20%, and operating costs by 10%. The use of electricity for heating and lighting greenhouses, and for running water pumps not only reduces labor costs, but also increases the yield per hectare of cultivated land. A product worth 100-150 soums is created for each soum of electricity. The use of electricity in grain farming increases labor productivity 3-4 times. The use of "OS-1", "OS-3", "OB-10" grain cleaning mechanisms in grain production reduces labor costs by 20-25%, and product costs by 15-35%. When drying grain, the labor cost is reduced by 30-40%, and the cost is reduced by 20-35%. The use of electricity in animal husbandry leads to a sharp reduction in labor costs. The use of electricity can be used for a number of tasks on the farm, including water supply, feeding animals in advance, milking cows, transporting various loads, shearing sheep wool, pre-treatment of milk, incubation, etc. allows to perform with the help of mechanisms. Automation of irrigation works increases the productivity of livestock by 10-15% and improves the quality of the obtained product. The use of electricity in the preliminary preparation of fodder for cattle reduces labor costs by 75-90% and improves the quality of feed [8]. The public is becoming more and more aware of the need to produce, protect and sell food to minimize negative changes in the environment and is more demanding in this regard. The advent of revolutionary scientific tools (such as biotechnological breakthroughs) provides the opportunity to significantly increase food production, reduce waste, and increase food security. The main challenge is to meet the increasing demands for food, other agricultural products and water in ways that contribute to long-term improvements in health and are sustainable, economical and competitive.

Despite the current global availability of enough food for all, many parts of the world, particularly regions, face significant challenges to ensure the availability and equitable distribution of safe, nutritious and affordable food supplies to meet health needs. must be overcome. rapid population growth. Despite advances in science and technology, contaminated food and water remain major public health problems today. Foodborne diseases are probably the most common health problems in the modern world and are important causes of economic decline. They are caused by a wide range of agents and cover all levels of severity, from mild to life-threatening diseases. However, only a small proportion of cases come to the attention of health services and even fewer cases are investigated. As a result, only about 10% of cases are reported in industrialized countries, and less than 1% of the total number of reported cases in developing countries. Electrification of livestock milking is also of great importance. When cows are milked with the help of milking machines, labor costs are saved, and the work of milkers is also reduced. 1 s. 4.4 man-hours are used for manual milking, 2.5 man-hours for milking using a milking machine, and 1.8 man-hours for milking in a milking parlor. The use of electricity in animal husbandry not only saves milking labor, but also increases the purity of milk. Shearing sheep's wool with the help of mechanisms increases labor productivity by 3-4 times, the quality of sheared wool is also much higher. As a result of lighting poultry farms at night with electricity, eggs obtained from chickens and ducks increase by 25-30 percent. The use of electric energy in auxiliary branches of the economy, including workshops, mills, wood sawing, etc., gives a great economic effect. According to research institutes, every billion kWh of electricity used in agriculture saves the labor of 700,000 able-bodied people per year and reduces production costs by 2 million. reduces to soum. The use of electricity plays a major role in improving the material and cultural well-being of rural residents, bringing rural culture closer to urban culture [9].

Effective use of electricity in agriculture is determined using the following indicators: labor productivity, product cost, net income per person per hour, income per 1 soum of production costs, additional capital expenditure. return period of 6% of energy resources and 27% of electricity are consumed in the branches of the agro-industrial complex, which produce more than 32% of the republic's gross domestic product. Although these indicators are several times lower than in developed countries, the energy capacity of product production remains high. There are objective and subjective reasons for this situation [10].

Technological innovations used in agricultural production are characterized by:

Solar and wind energy systems. In order to achieve energy independence, the use of renewable energy sources in agriculture is increasing. Solar panels are important in the operation of irrigation systems and electrical equipment. Recent years have seen significant growth in the integration of solar energy into agricultural practices, offering sustainable solutions that reduce environmental impact and increase crop yields. One of the most important uses of solar energy in agriculture is the use of solar irrigation systems. These systems use solar panels to capture sunlight, which is then converted into electricity to power water pumps. By ensuring a reliable and environmentally friendly water supply, farmers can effectively irrigate their crops even in remote areas with limited access to traditional energy sources.

Sun drying is an ancient technique used to preserve agricultural produce without relying on electricity or fuel. By harnessing solar energy, farmers can build low-cost drying facilities that passively absorb sunlight and remove moisture from crops such as fruits, vegetables, and grains. This process extends shelf life, reduces waste, and allows farmers to store excess produce for future sale or consumption. Greenhouses are essential for year-round cultivation in regions with extreme climates. Combining solar panels with greenhouses increases their stability and efficiency. Solar panels can power ventilation systems, heating and cooling equipment, which can minimize energy costs while maintaining optimal conditions for crop growth.

In addition to crops, solar energy is also used in livestock. Solar panels can be used in barns and animal shelters to provide electricity for lighting, heating and pumping water. This off-grid approach not only reduces operating costs, but also reduces the carbon footprint of the entire livestock process. Innovative farmers are introducing solar-powered pest control methods to reduce reliance on chemical pesticides. For example, solar-powered insect traps attract and trap pests, preventing them from damaging crops. In addition, solar energy can power scare devices with motion sensors and audible alarms to deter birds and other wildlife from feeding on produce.

Drones and automated systems. With the help of electrified drones and automated equipment, the effectiveness of crop monitoring, pest control and fertilization processes is increasing. Currently, cultivated land in Uzbekistan is 4.5 million hectares, and pasture land is more than 20 million hectares. Based on this, there is a possibility that the size of the spray drone market in the country will reach about 12,500 units. Taking into account the experience of developing countries, the use of UAV technologies and artificial intelligence in the field of agriculture in Uzbekistan can provide a 2-5% increase in GDP in the next 5 years, which will amount to 1.8-4.5 billion is a dollar (picture 3).

Picture 3. Drone used in agriculture.

Save time (3 times), water resources (up to 20 percent) and sprayers (pesticides by 60 percent), eliminate crop damage from wheeled vehicles (up to 5 percent), irrigation and it is estimated that cotton and grain productivity will increase by 30%, fruits by 15%, and rice by 25% due to proper planting. In the fuel and energy sector, drones will be necessary for monitoring power lines, solar power plants and pipelines, construction and repair works, and detecting illegal activities. The use of drones in the construction sector accelerates the construction planning, monitoring and control processes by up to 10%, saves financial resources by 5% due to the automation of topographic photography, inspection and quality control processes, and also reduces the risks to the life and health of construction workers. Minimizes up to 20 percent [11].

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The main production techniques and technologies in this area are somewhat outdated. A modern energy and electrotechnological equipment system, informed by scientific research, has yet to be developed. Most existing equipment and technologies do not fully meet the current demand. Challenges persist in their usage, repair, adjustment, and the retraining of personnel. Addressing these issues requires fundamental and scientific-technical research, as well as the development of organizational and technical measures, including the following directions to promote efficient energy use and the creation of energy-saving equipment and technologies tailored to the needs of agriculture:

Developing a unified state energy policy program focused on advancing the agrarian sector. This includes organizing a scientific and technical team of experienced experts and scientists to coordinate research efforts for its implementation.

Evaluating the efficiency of energy resources, including electricity, in the production, processing, and storage of agricultural products. Establishing methodological frameworks to integrate energy resources and consumers into a single, cohesive system.

To address these and other challenges, it is essential to enhance gross production in the agro-industrial complex by implementing solutions such as increasing seed production, improving breeding techniques, enhancing soil fertility, advancing land reclamation, and undertaking other agrotechnical measures. These initiatives must replace low-productivity, labor-intensive practices with high-performance, energy-efficient equipment and accelerated technological processes. Furthermore, direct use of electrophysical effects should be expanded to achieve new technological outcomes.

Special attention should also be given to the adoption of non-traditional energy sources, particularly solar energy, to increase the energy input in product production. As the world faces the dual challenges of climate change and the need for sustainable agricultural practices, solar energy has emerged as a vital ally. Its integration into agriculture reduces reliance on traditional energy sources, enabling farmers to become self-reliant and environmentally responsible. By harnessing solar power, the agricultural industry can take significant strides toward a greener and more sustainable future.

Solar energy in agriculture is a win-win solution, benefiting farmers, consumers, and the environment alike.

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